

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article presents the technology used in teaching speaking and its effects to students as they learn to speak in English. Results revealed that students are taught to speak in English using the technologies of today such as video conferencing, email correspondence, social media interaction and real-time actual emceeing and onstage speaking performances where students are engaged in real academic and professional situations. Apparently, the researcher found that the technology used in teaching speaking can be aligned with the communicative way of teaching which allows students to convey themselves in a skillful and competent way of communication.

Keywords: phenomenon, effects; technology; teaching speaking; focus group discussion, fluency, accuracy, abilities, multilevel.

Speaking is one of the macro skills in English that instructors and students must polish. A good speech is accompanied by fluency and accuracy which students must learn and enhance competitively. Teaching speaking has been given much importance at school for many years. It has been part of every curriculum but it is undervalued that teaching speaking is only through memorization and repetition of drills focusing on the fluency of the production of sounds. However, in these recent times that the English language is dubbed to be the second most popular language with approximately 400 million native speakers, teaching speaking requires innovative ways and methods rather than teaching speaking through memorization and parroting.

This kind of speech activity, like written speech, has received the attention it deserves since society's overall informatization has a big impact on our lives overall and the educational system. When you are outside of the linguistic setting and have proficiency in written language, you can use your knowledge of a foreign language to communicate with native speakers utilizing contemporary communication tools like the Internet, email, SMS, and more. Students learn how to master written communication in the target language by having the chance to write both official and personal letters, as well as by having to complete questionnaires and document forms. Following E.G. Azimov and A.N. Shchukin, we define written speech as a type of communication that is connected to the perception and representation of ideas in graphic [1]. "To teach students to write in a foreign language the same texts that an educated person can write in their native language: filling out questionnaires, writing various types of letters and replies to them, including both personal and official, compiling an autobiography / resumes, writing applications (including for employment, enrollment in studies, etc.), writing reviews, annotations, reports, writing compositions/essays, writing greeting cards, notes," states E.N. Solovyova in her list of the objectives of writing instruction. [3]

Expanding students' horizons and knowledge, mastering the cultural and intellectual readiness to create a written speech work, and the formation of authentic ideas about the subject content, speech style, and graphic form of written text are among the goals of teaching written speech in a foreign language. These goals also include teaching students the necessary graphic automatisms, speech-thinking skills, and the ability to formulate their thoughts in accordance with the written style. Information technology has made it possible to bring the foreign language learning process closer to reality than it has ever been. As a result, among the things that computers can do are perceive and analyze information, store specific data in memory, reproduce audio and video content, and more. In addition to the stated abilities, [6]

Information technology is used in English lessons with the following objectives: to increase student motivation to learn the language; to develop speech competence; to increase the amount of linguistic knowledge; to expand the amount of knowledge about the sociocultural specifics of the country where the language is being studied; and to develop the ability and readiness to study English independently [2]. Information technology tools enable the efficient completion of a wide range of pedagogic duties during foreign language lessons. A computer and other IT technologies, for instance, can assist a teacher in improving their students' writing and reading comprehension, help pupils expand their vocabulary more efficiently, and foster the development of long-term desire for learning a foreign language. Simultaneously, a key responsibility of the instructor is to establish an environment in which each student can acquire a language practically, to choose instructional strategies that will allow each student to demonstrate his or her creativity and activity, and to enable him or her to engage in more cognitive activity during the process of learning a foreign language. [4]

P.V. Sisoiev lists eight didactic characteristics of contemporary ICTs in his writings that have an impact on how intensely foreign language instruction is conducted.

1. Internet information resources are multilingual and multicultural. It will be possible to put the principle of dialogue of cultures into practice by studying, contrasting, and comparing materials about various cultural groups as well as variations of the language being studied. Students will also develop an understanding of the linguistic and cultural diversity of the nation where the language is being studied as well as cultural diversity as the standard for the coexistence of cultures in the contemporary multicultural world.

2. Information sources on the Internet that are multilevel. Because material on the Internet may be found at all degrees of linguistic complexity.

3. A range of useful Internet resource kinds. Materials in the form of text, graphics and audiovisuals show you how to gather the information you need from variety of sources.

4. Resources in multimedia. It is possible to hear native speakers' speech and become familiar with the culture of the nation where the language being learned is spoken thanks to multimedia resources.

5. Document hypertext structure. This feature makes it possible to navigate through a lot of information quickly.

6. The potential to establish a private user area. Establishing and managing personal profiles on several social media platforms and engaging in diverse instant messaging services can help you enhance your capacity to self-introduce, discuss your hobbies, represent your nation and culture, and more.

7. Asynchronous and synchronous communication organization is possible. Chat rooms and Skype can be used to achieve synchronous communication. Asynchronous communication happens on blogs, forums, and email accounts. This characteristic can be used, for instance, to foster interaction and communication between students and their international classmates or between students and a teacher.

8. The potential for information and methodological support processes to be automated, as well as the ability to organize and administer the control and management of students' educational activities. The control and partial or complete automation of educational operations is made possible by modern IT systems [7] The most often utilized IT tools in education are computer-based multimedia projector demonstrations of electronic textbooks and manuals, Internet-based educational resources, video and audio equipment, electronic encyclopedias and reference books, DVDs and CDs with images and illustrations, testing software, research projects, and research works.

Furthermore, a number of online simulators are regarded as useful tools for improving writing abilities. By using them, various IT-based didactic properties and functions can be implemented, including multi-level, multimedia, hypertext structure, various functional resource types, automation of information and methodological support processes, organization of the management and control of students' educational activities, creation of individual educational trajectories, and skill development for independent learning activities. The following should be recognized as some of the interactive tasks that make use of information and communication technologies: producing interactive polls, blogging and commenting, wiki sites, email exchanges with the teacher and other students, and interactive exercises to improve spelling during reciprocal learning. It is important to stress that the active integration of IT tools into the educational process amicably coexists with traditional teaching methods throughout the whole training period, rather than negating them in any way.

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